

Appendix Table 6. Turkey element percentages for selected structures.

Structures selected for Tables 2-7 include those with the highest numbers of specific taxa, as well as a range of building types.

	Q-152 temple	Q-54 hall	Q-97 hall	Q-92 house	Q-58 temple	Q-95 temple	R-106 palace
breast	1.4%	0.2%	0.2%		0.3%		0.4%
breast/pelvis	30.2%						
limb	4.8%	27.8%	27.8%	40.7%	29.0%	16.4%	23.3%
metapodial/phalanges	15.9%	18.7%	18.7%	17.5%	22.5%	22.4%	26.9%
pelvis	7.0%	0.7%	0.7%	0.3%	0.6%	1.3%	1.1%
shoulder	7.3%	4.0%	4.0%	6.3%	2.1%	4.4%	6.8%
tarsal		0.2%	0.2%			0.3%	
upper limb	15.8%	12.9%	12.9%	8.5%	16.0%	11.7%	9.7%
upper limb lower	13.2%	34.3%	34.3%	26.0%	29.3%	42.6%	31.9%
vertebra	4.3%	1.2%	1.2%	0.8%	0.3%	0.9%	